

IMPROVING THE SYSTEMATIC ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF THE PROCESSES OF DEVELOPING SPIRITUAL AND SOCIAL ACTIVITY AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the application of cooperation technology in practical processes and its importance, based on paying attention to the factors and criteria that are considered important in the formation of social activity in the student. At the same time, the reader will learn from this article about the meanings of the concept of “social activity” that are interpreted today, views on its importance. The student analyzes how the formation of social activity of young people is becoming a necessity today and its reasons.*

Keywords: *social activity, student, organization, mobility, student personality.*

In our republic, special attention is paid to the improvement of the content of higher education and personnel training processes based on advanced foreign experiences, to the development of social competencies in students as an important direction of spiritual and educational work. At the same time, there is a need to improve the pedagogical mechanisms of achieving a full understanding of the social importance of students' professional activities, finding a suitable solution to social demands and obligations. In the “Strategy of Actions” aimed at the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to raise physically healthy, spiritually and intellectually developed, independent-thinking young people, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm outlook on life, in the process of deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society. Significant and important tasks were set, such as increasing social activity. This requires clarifying the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the development of social activity of students, the pedagogical model of the development of social activity, and the use of interactive and modern technologies in the formation of the content of classes outside the auditorium that's why the most important things are studying what and how social activity is done and the factors and criteria of forming social activity of students, and applying technologies. The concept of “social activity” today is interpreted in a broad and narrow sense. Social activity in a broad sense is a quality that reflects the level of sociality of a person, i.e. his connections with social integrity, willingness to act in the interests of society, the depth of acceptance of public interests, and in a narrow sense, social activity is understood as a quality that expresses the connection of a person with a certain social community. We will consider the category of social activity in this scientific article in a narrow sense. The modern educational space today is professionally competent, socially active and competitive personnel, specialists who are ready to provide a stable, safe, successful society, as society is putting more complex tasks before humanity. In such processes, the society needs professionals to determine their own destiny, to be self-aware, to think freely and independently, in other words, to be socially active individuals. Based on this, it can be said that society needs modern knowledge. Independent, ethical, proactive people who can make responsible decisions in the chosen situation, predict their possible consequences; choose methods of cooperation, mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, develop a

sense of responsibility for country's destiny, in a word so to speak, socially active individuals will be in the center of the field in this place. In this regard, today the sociality of the individual is increasing more and more and is gaining importance. The student personality is consciously aimed at solving the problems facing the society, and since the tribe is a social group that manifests itself in activities of high social importance, they play an important role in the life of society.

Student youth are considered unique as a social group. It follows that they embody all the characteristics of youth, and also confirms this with the following characteristics:

activities related to education at the university;

“the most educated youth group;

Reserve for replenishment of knowledge workers;

An integral part of the intelligentsia;

heterogeneity of social origin;

self-awareness of a certain group;

Community of interest and subculture. It is necessary to form the social activity of students. Of course, on the one hand, it is permissible to act taking into account the changing social characteristics, and on the other hand, the specific characteristics of this socio-demographic group, its internal stratification, its place and role in society, as well as among young people solving the existing conflicting aspect of needs and its implementation as a social entity opportunities should not be overlooked. A number of factors are considered important in forming the social activity of students. This factors: the desire for self-realization of young people, effective public policy on youth, and also interesting and influential people for young people. At the same time, we also face factors that hinder the formation of social activity among students. For example, disbelief, indifference to the problems of older age groups, lack of trust in authority, indifference towards the students themselves.

It is also important to manage the formation of social activity in students. In this case, the main criterion of the effectiveness of managing the social formation of students is the high level of student activity in all types of activities and the high level of compatibility of interests with the interests of other social entities. Therefore, based on these recognitions, it is possible to witness the importance of paying close attention to the necessary factors in the formation of social activity in students. Based on these factors, the application of collaborative technology in the process will be effective. Because the idea of cooperative learning is not only to do the tasks together, but also to read, search and learn together. To increase the social activity of students, teaching on the basis of this technology is to teach every student to fundamentally intense mental work, to think creatively and independently, to educate consciousness and independence as a person, to create a sense of personal dignity in every student. Strengthening confidence, paying attention to educational processes as a result imply the formation of a sense of responsibility in learning.

There is a lot of supporting information on the topic of systematic organization and management of spiritual and social activity development processes. The most important cases:

Strengthening the educational system: It is important to adapt the educational system to the development of spiritual and social activity for young people. Specific methods and programs of education should be defined.

Application of past knowledge: Youth ensure their development by applying past knowledge. Training programs should help increase this process.

Learning through games and attractions: Learning through games and attractions is one of the most effective ways to develop moral and social activity in young people. This method increases the interest of young people and makes their learning easy and interesting.

Grandfather's provisions: Grandfather's provisions are very important in the development of spiritual and social activity for young people. They help in the development of emotional expression, interactivity and social participation.

Mentoring and planning: Mentoring and planning help young people play an important role in facilitating their development. Mentoring helps to expand communication with students in all areas and increase their spiritual and social activity.

In short, educating the growing young generation in the spirit of social activity is one of the urgent tasks of today. As defined in the basic law of independent Uzbekistan, the society's perspective, development and development path is to establish a legal, democratic, humane civil society. Building such a society requires students to be organized, proactive, flexible, and generally speaking, social depends in many ways on the formation of activity skills.

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